

DETERMINING THE MICROCLIMATE PARAMETERS OF CLOTHING UNDER THE NATIONAL ATTIRE OF TASHKENT-FERGANA WOMEN AND ANALYZING THE PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF TRADITIONAL FABRICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17233648>

Abstract. *This research is dedicated to determining the physical and mechanical properties of fabrics used in women's clothing and the parameters of the microclimate under clothing in Tashkent and Fergana during the late 19th and early 20th centuries. The types of fabrics used for outerwear, dresses, and undergarments of women in Tashkent and Fergana were identified. Their physical and mechanical properties were studied. Specifically, the air permeability levels (T , °C) of fabrics such as banoras, beqasam, nimshoyi, and adras were analyzed. Additionally, the parameters of the microclimate under clothing were determined at temperatures of +30°C and -10°C, including air humidity (ϕ , %) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels in the clothing cavity. The microclimate in the clothing cavity was measured in laboratories using standard tests on materials and clothing items. Tests conducted with the use of clothing can assess the user's subjective reaction to it. In fact, these experimental studies of clothing are carried out in special microclimate chambers. The chamber design allows for modeling and controlling the meteorological and specific parameters of the external environment, such as air movement, temperature, humidity, pressure changes, the concentration of harmful substances, and more. This device enables comprehensive detection of temperature, humidity, and carbon monoxide concentration within the suit cavity, transmitting the data directly to a mobile phone application via Bluetooth. Data on the temperature, humidity, and carbon dioxide parameters of the microclimate under the clothing are transmitted to a mobile phone. The microclimate parameters under multi-layered women's garments in different regions were measured at +30°C and -10°C using the CJMCU-811 CCS811 device. As a result, it was found that the clothing of women in the Tashkent-Fergana region had a higher CO concentration of 618 ppm at +30°C compared to other regions, and a lower CO concentration of 1212 ppm in the microclimate under the clothing at -10°C compared to other regions.*

Key words: *national, costume, region, banoras, adras, beqasam, nimshoyi, fabric, temperature, humidity, microclimate, experiment.*

Introduction

National Costume of Tashkent and Fergana in the 19th–20th Century.

Women's Costume. One of the functions of clothing culture relates to the transformation of women's attire. Our research, as well as conversations with elderly grandmothers, has shown that in the past, young women wore dresses with raised collars and triangular-shaped decorative stitching on the edges until they gave birth to their first child.

At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, dresses with pleated chests became fashionable, indicating the active participation of our national clothing in transformational processes. Today, dresses with pleated chests remain popular among our women. According to researchers in this field, women in the past typically wore a single dress at home. During cooler seasons or winter, they wore two or more dresses. When attending gatherings, weddings, or other festive ceremonies, women from well-off families would wear up to three dresses. The sleeves of these dresses had decorative layers. The first dress had the longest sleeves, the second dress had slightly shorter sleeves, and the third dress had even shorter ones. This layering of sleeves was designed to enhance the beauty of the women, serving as an aesthetic feature of their attire.

According to T.A. Abdullaev and S.A. Khasanova, "If women wanted to showcase their rich wardrobe, they would take several dresses with them when visiting guests and change their outfits from time to time. Sometimes, women also wore an underdress made of white cotton fabric beneath their main dress." [1].

The length of dresses varied: older women wore dresses long enough to touch the ground, while younger women wore relatively shorter ones." [2]. This demonstrates how clothing culture has evolved over centuries based on age and social status.

Women's attire, like that of other regions, included a dress (ko'ylak), trousers (lozim), and outer garments such as a mursak or to'n. For going outside, women wore a paranji. Head coverings included various scarves, while footwear consisted of mahsi (soft leather boots) and kavush (slippers). Additionally, jewelry was an essential part of their adornment. In daily life, women typically wore a to'n or mursak depending on their age, along with a single dress, trousers, and a headscarf. For festive occasions and ceremonies, they dressed in garments made from expensive fabrics. When stepping outside, women covered themselves with a paranji to avoid being seen by unfamiliar men.

In Tashkent, women's undergarments included a loose dress (ko'ylak) and wide trousers (ishton-lozim). According to historical sources, women's dresses in this region came in four different styles: Straight-cut dress (to'g'ri ko'ylak) – a simple, straight-cut design, Open-front dress (oldi ochiq ko'ylak) – worn by married and elderly women, featuring an open neckline. Keptak dress (keptakli ko'ylak) – designed for young girls and teenage girls, distinguished by a horizontal yoke. Mullacha dress (mullacha ko'ylak) – traditionally worn by madrasa students.

This dress featured a standing collar (tik yoqa) and a layered skirt (qat-qat etak) with a patched bodice (ulama lif). All dresses had long sleeves. In the late 19th century, it became customary to wear very wide and long traditionally cut dresses, as well as straight-cut dresses. The narrowing of the dress at the sides resulted in a slightly flared hem.

Over time, the width of the chest and hem of the dress became uniform. To embellish the dresses, embroidery, monochrome trim, or braided ribbons were sewn onto the collar area. Typically, tassel-adorned trim (popuk shokilali jiyak) was used for young girls' and married women's dresses, while simple ribbon decorations (tasma) were added to the dresses of elderly women.

A qubbacha-shaped silver ornament called peshauz was attached to the tassel at the waist of a woman's dress. Inside the peshauz, women carried small essential items such as a needle case (mo'ychinak), a toothpick (tishkovlagich), a perfume bottle (atir shishachasi), and keys. The vertical collars of the dress were fastened at the top with ties (bog'ichlar). One important tradition in Tashkent was the ritual of changing dresses after the wedding ceremony. After marriage, the

bride would replace her maiden dress with a woman's dress before arriving at the groom's home. However, in Fergana, this transition took much longer—the young bride continued wearing her maiden dress until the birth of her first child.

The standing-collar dress (*tik yoqali ko'ylak*) became fashionable starting in 1880. Women's dresses, made from luxurious fabrics such as *kalguy*, were designed with a standing collar sewn both at the front and back. This design allowed the dress to be worn reversibly, so if the dress became worn or dirty, it could be turned inside out and still be worn. This type of attire was primarily used by nomadic women.

The standing collar and belted waist designs, along with pleated collars between the sleeves, emerged under the influence of Tatar fashion. By the 1890s, pleated chest dresses (*ulama ko'krak burmali ko'ylak*) became popular. This style of dress suited women of all ages, and over time, it became a part of the national costume, still worn today by women, including elderly ones. For women's dresses, a variety of unique and valuable fabrics were used, including *calami*, *xomsurp*, delicate *dokadek*, silk, *kalguy*, satin, *adras*, and imported materials such as *bakhmal*, silk, and *kimkhob* fabrics from Russia, England, France, India, Turkey, and China (see Fig. 1).

Bo'z adras fabric Olacha fabric Kalami fabric Xon atlas Adras
(100% - cotton) (100% - cotton) (99% - cotton, 1% - ipak) (100% - ipak) (semi-silk fabrics
50% - ipak, 50% - cotton)

Fig 1. A selection of unique and luxurious fabrics for women's dresses.

In addition to the dress, trousers (*ishton*) and *lozims* (wide trousers) were an integral part of the attire for women of all ages. In the 19th century, the upper part of the *lozims* was wide, gradually narrowing towards the bottom. These *lozims* covered the shoes and had a thick waistband (*baxya*) designed to hold a belt (*ishtonbog'*). The hem of the *lozims* was decorated with trim. Typically, *lozims* were made from *chit*, *adras*, or silk fabrics.

The outer garments worn by women from Fergana and Tashkent included *peshvon*, *mursak*, *to'n*, and *chopon*, which evolved into *beshbel*, *kamzul*, and *nimcha* by the early 20th century. Throughout the year, women wore cotton-quilted *chopons* or *to'ns*. These garments were usually one-piece, with long sleeves and loosely stitched seams.

During the winter season, heavily quilted *chopons* with thick stitching were also worn. These garments had large stitches that were quilted both vertically and horizontally, forming a checkered pattern. The style of women's *chopons* was similar to that of men's, but the sleeves were long and narrow. Additionally, the edges of the *chopon* were decorated with black fabric trim (*mag'iz*).

Unfortunately, the *peshvon*-type *chopon* has not survived to the present day. It is known that this type of *chopon* was similar to the *mursak* and was part of the wedding attire collection. The sleeves of the *peshvon* were long, and it did not feature a clasp or fastening on the front. However, like men's *chopons*, the collar of the *peshvon* was quilted. In fact, the *peshvon* was worn draped over the head. This type of *chopon* was made without lining.

In Fergana and Tashkent, one distinctive type of outer garment for women was the **open-front, sleeveless, lace-collared mursak (also called mirsak or misak).

The key difference between these mursaks and those worn by women in Bukhara was that the chest and neck area of the Tashkent and Fergana mursaks could easily be opened. Additionally, the front part of the mursak's skirt featured small clasps. When worn, the skirts of the mursak touched each other, leaving the chest area exposed. Mursaks were worn both in winter and summer.

However, there was a difference between the summer and winter versions of the mursak. The summer mursak was made with a thin cotton lining, while the winter mursak was designed to be larger and warmer. The mursak was primarily worn during festivals and ceremonies, and women also wore it for special occasions such as weddings, bride greetings, and other ceremonial events. By the 1920s, however, the mursak became reserved for funeral and mourning ceremonies. It was specifically used to cover women's coffins, and this tradition has been preserved to the present day .

Both the chopon and mursak were made from national fabrics such as threaded gazlama, floral adras, silk, or beqasaba, and their designs were distinct from other types of chopons. Paranji was also considered part of women's attire during this period. Before the 1917 revolution, paranji was commonly worn as an outdoor garment by women, serving as a form of cover when walking in public.

There is also information that the use of the paranji in Tashkent started later than in other regions. Today, the paranjis preserved in museums are evidence of the widespread use of this garment in the past. A distinctive feature of the Tashkent paranji is that its collar was decorated with two rows of trim, setting it apart from those in other areas.

Compared to the paranjis from other regions, the Tashkent and Fergana paranjis were much more elegant and simple, as they were not adorned with embroidery. For this reason, the most valuable fabrics were chosen for these paranjis, and the simplicity of the fabric itself became the main form of decoration.

The chachvon, a rectangular and long headscarf, was usually made from black horsehair, with the edges adorned with satin or duxoba fabric. The bottom part of the chachvon was decorated with Iroqi-style embroidery. Over time, to further embellish the chachvon, machine-stitched chain embroidery was added, which was called popop. To cover the face, a button and cord were used at the top of the chachvon, and a paranji was draped over it.

In Tashkent, it was mandatory for women to wear the paranji from the age of nine (puberty) until old age. The color and decoration of the paranji could indicate the woman's age. For girls, the paranji was usually made from red cloth or other inexpensive fabrics. For young women, the paranji was made from fabrics like small-striped blue, black, or bluish-white domestic nimshoyi fabric, and sometimes from silvery-grey banoras fabric.

By the end of the 19th century, expensive paranjis were primarily made from factory-produced fabrics, including woven silk, kimxob, and embroidered Chinese atlas. The lining of the paranji was made from inexpensive cloth, and a colored adras border was stitched at the bottom, about 0.5 centimeters wide. Initially, the decorations on the paranji were very simple. Typically, the collar, skirt, sleeves, and edges of the paranji were decorated with trim or mag'iz. By the beginning of the 20th century, paranjis became fashionable in wide, light-colored designs.

In decorating the paranjis, intricate serbar patterns and black floral trims were used. The flowers on the trims were embroidered with silk threads. The sleeves of the paranji featured fake

pockets, decorated with popuk (a type of ornamental beadwork), and designs like snake patterns and much-nusxa flowers were embroidered on them.

The old paranjis were long and covered the entire body. Over time, however, their length gradually became shorter.

Every culture naturally evolves and develops under the influence of other cultures, adapting to new social and historical conditions. However, in all cases, national identity must remain paramount. After the Central Asia region was conquered by Tsarist Russia, new types of clothing began to emerge, blending with our traditional garments. For example, kamzul and nimcha appeared during this period, and these garments started to incorporate elements of our national spirit, traditions, and culture. The fact that these kamzuls were made from national fabrics like bakhmal and beqasam ensured that national identity remained a prominent feature. In particular, the decoration of the collars and buttons of kamzuls with national patterns and embroidery played a significant role in securing their place in the ensemble of traditional attire.

At the end of the 19th century, young women wore headscarves made of white cotton, with the corners decorated with edging. These headscarves were distinguished by their unique stitching techniques compared to other types of headscarves.

For example, iroqi duro'ya, yurma zanjir embroidery, and sanama iroqi methods were used in the production of these headscarves. Women wore these types of headscarves until they had two or three children, after which they would switch to simpler white headscarves without embroidery.

In the 19th century, women with two or three children wore sochpopukli kulyuta, a traditional headwear. Kulyutas were usually brightly decorated, small, circular in shape, and had a special pouch at the back to secure the hair. Young women could wear two headscarves simultaneously. The larger headscarf was folded corner to corner and placed on the head without being tied, with its two corners hanging down at the chest. On top of this, a smaller colorful headscarf, known as durra, was tied.

For older women, wearing three headscarves simultaneously was a common practice. The first scarf's corners were draped over the waist, while a small scarf was tied on the forehead. Over the second scarf, a dakana or loki (headpiece) was wrapped. Toshkent's elderly women's headscarves (sallas) were different from men's in style, with the end of the scarf either hanging down to the pech (fireplace) or tucked into the head wrap. Wearing headscarves like this signified elegance and grandeur, especially with the use of durra (decorative headpieces) on the forehead.

By the early 20th century, the practice of wrapping salla had faded out, and women began wearing two headscarves instead. Doppi (traditional hats) also became a main headwear for women in Tashkent and Farg'ona regions. Interestingly, women in these areas did not wear doppi until 1917. The doppi became fashionable only during the Soviet era. Before that, young girls wore headpieces decorated with feathers (pat) and tumors. In making doppi, various embroidery techniques and decorative stitching methods were used to embellish them, giving them distinct regional features.

The following is written in the Uzbek National Encyclopedia: "In the later stages of our social and historical development, the 'iroqi' technique became widespread in the making of 'do'ppis'. 'Iroqi' is a type of embroidery stitch used primarily for 'do'ppis', collars, and small embroidery. This stitch is mainly in the shape of an 'X', and it is widely used in patterns resembling rug flowers. This technique is further divided into two types: 'Sanama' and 'Chizma'. The 'Sanama' type is mainly used in making 'do'ppis', where the pattern is created by counting the threads of the fabric without drawing it out. The 'Chizma' type is a form where patterns are drawn on the fabric

with a pencil before stitching. The 'Iroqi' embroidery technique is widely spread in our republic, with the 'Iroqi' stitch being known since ancient times in 'Shahrisabz embroidery', and later spreading to places such as Tashkent, Samarkand, Fergana, Surkhandarya, and other areas." [3].

In recent years, in the southern regions, there has been a widespread use of the iroqi technique for embroidering flowers and designs on scarves by girls and women. The method of creating decoration by striking the fabric is called "piltadozlik," and it is widely used in the Samarkand and Boysun do'ppichilik schools. According to experts: "Piltadozlik, in the past, was associated with the nomadic lifestyle of pastoralists, and the method of pitalash (binding) was widely used in tents for fastening reeds. This technique has also found its expression in the examples of practical art in the local culture." [4].

The ethno-social and cultural development, along with the evolution of clothing and its transformation into new societies, shows that do'ppis (traditional headwear) had a local significance until the first half of the 20th century. The do'ppis of each tribe or specific region exhibited distinctive characteristics. Do'ppis from Tashkent, the Fergana Valley, Samarkand, Shahrisabz, and Boysun differed in terms of color, patterns, sewing methods, shapes, and other aspects. The ancient nature of the do'ppi and its unique shape in each geographical region made it widely recognized in the social and historical development process, often associated with the name of the region where it was produced. For example, names like "Chust do'ppi," "Andijan do'ppi," "Kokand do'ppi," and so on.

Today, experts acknowledge that do'ppis are divided into six types based on their shape, pattern, and unique characteristics, which reflect regional distinctions. These include the do'ppis of Tashkent, Fergana, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khorezm, and Kashkadarya-Surkhondarya regions. Starting from the early 20th century, as commodity- money relations developed among the peoples of our region, compact and elegant do'ppis began to be sold in various markets and gained popularity among the inhabitants of different regions.

By the 20th century, the appearance of sewing machines in our country led to changes in the folk applied art, bringing about new techniques, schools, patterns, and motifs. As a result, the applied art of Uzbek women, particularly the art of do'ppichilik (making and decorating do'ppis), today differs sharply not only from the traditions of other countries but even from those of Kazakh and Kyrgyz women. [5]

According to the traditions of the Tashkent and Fergana valleys, jewelry adornments were worn from childhood. The number of pieces varied depending on the woman's age and social status. During this period, rings, earrings, necklaces, and bracelets were common jewelry items. Rings were usually adorned with colorful stones or glass and made in large sizes. Bracelets, made of gold and silver, were sometimes decorated with intricate patterns. In Tashkent, dome-shaped earrings and large hoop-shaped qoshg'ar pendants were fashionable. The qoshg'ar pendants had unique decorations, with the lower half embellished with beadwork and enamel. The origin of these earrings is linked to the fugitives who fled from China during its rule and settled in the Fergana Valley, carrying their traditions with them.

At the end of the 19th century, new types of earrings became fashionable, including jiida-shaped earrings and earrings made of three interconnected vertical plates. These earrings were usually decorated with glass stones and shokilas (mirror earrings). By the early 20th century, it became trendy to wear gold earrings with red stones and small pearl-like shokilas. Up until the early 20th century, it was also fashionable to wear small-hoop earrings with multiple tiny stones. Additionally, a necklace made of several pearls, known as jevak, became one of the most beloved

adornments for women. During this period, wearing a decorative zebigardon with coins and beads also became popular. The zebigardon is a delicate necklace made of five rows of chains, adorned with seven fine medallions. The peshovez (a small dome-shaped pendant) and kalitli shokilas (key-shaped decorations) on a peshxalta (silver pouch) are also considered chest adornments. These ornaments were worn on the final part of the vertical seams of women's dresses. Hair was also adorned, often with a pair of zarkokil (earring-like ornaments) placed on both sides of the face or woven into the braids. However, hairpieces made of woven shokilas, passed through silver tubes, were more commonly used. In the Fergana Valley and Tashkent, tillabargak (golden headbands) and tillaqosh (golden forehead decorations) were worn as forehead adornments. Additionally, ornaments like zulfizar and peshanagajak were used as complementary pieces. The adornments worn on the dress included a rectangular-shaped piece with leaf-like shokilas connected with turquoise and pearls, called tillabargak. This name was given because of the leaf motifs on the piece. Additionally, the tillaqosh was considered a very beautiful ornament. It featured interlinked eyebrow-shaped diadems with a lattice-like crown at the top, decorated with turquoise, making it a piece that enhanced the beauty and elegance of women. The tillaqosh was mainly worn by women, although in Tashkent, young girls also wore this adornment during festive occasions.

By the early 20th century, interest in jewelry began to decline. This was because, by this time, the trend of wearing silk, pleated, and wrinkled headscarves had become popular. The new scarves did not match well with the traditional forehead adornments.

Hairstyles. In the 19th century, women of different age groups had their own unique hairstyles. In Tashkent and Kokand, young girls would braid their hair into small braids and wear part of it in front. Women with two children would braid their hair into 4-5 braids. Middle-aged women were required to braid their hair into 2 braids. Married women would braid their hair in two pairs to prevent them from interfering. Over time, older women would separate their hair and create large braids at the top of their forehead. Widows would wear their hair loose and decorate it with a chain of beads.

Women's footwear also holds an important place in the composition of traditional clothing. Footwear has long served not only to protect from heat, cold, and dampness, but also to ensure safety. For example, shoes were used as a means of protection from various injuries and, when necessary, as a defense weapon. As a result of social and historical development, women's footwear has evolved into different forms, one of which is the "mahs" (traditional slippers). The mahs was very convenient for our conditions and became widely popular. The lower part of the trousers would be tucked into the mahs. Wealthy people wore "iroqi mahs," made of leather, while ordinary people wore wooden slippers during the winter.

In the first half of the 20th century, mahs were worn by specific social groups who gave them value and embellishment. Some mahs were made of simple leather with basic coloring, while others were dyed in various colors and had lacquered tops. When worn with high-heeled "amirkon" slippers, these mahs not only reflected the quality of the product but also indicated the wearer's social status and functions in society. [6]

Uzbekistan's abr fabrics.

The origins of the "abr" fabric in Central Asia are difficult to pinpoint. Older artisans and masters of the abr technique consider this method to be ancient. Based on the Ajanta paintings, this fabric dyeing method was known as early as the first centuries AD.

The term "abr" (translated from Persian as "cloud") appears in literary sources from the 16th century as a pattern name. According to one legend, abr patterns were initially inspired by the

image of clouds floating on the surface of a pool of water, while another version suggests that it was inspired by the spread of oil droplets on the water's surface. It is possible that these images were first reflections of the rainbow and were linked to ancient embroidery traditions such as "abri-bahor" (spring cloud).

The technique of dyeing the thread for "abr" fabric is quite complex. The thread, measuring 200-300 meters in length, is distributed into small bundles called "libit" on a special loom. Depending on the fabric's density and width, each libit contains 40-60 threads. The libits are paired in twos and wrapped around the horizontal bars of the loom. The spacing between the bars is linked to the pattern's repeat (1.4 to 2.25 meters). The artist-abrband marks half of the design with horizontal lines using a fine wooden tool and black ink mixed with water, working along the vertical axis. The master does not use stencils or sketches in this process.

Ancient fabrics were dyed with plant-based dyes, such as madder root, pomegranate peel, walnut husks, marigold, indigo, and cochineal. These dyes were resistant to fading in sunlight and water. Using natural dyes, it was possible to create a full spectrum of colors. They harmonized with each other, remaining vibrant and lasting without fading.

According to the weaving method, abr fabrics are divided into two main groups: garniture and atlas weaving. In garniture weaving, silk fabrics ("shoyi") and half-silk fabrics ("adras" or "dagir") are produced. In half-silk fabrics, the warp thread is made of natural silk, while the weft thread is made of cotton thread, which is either white or brightly colored. The weft thread is thicker than the warp, which gives the fabric a textured surface. Silk was commonly used for women's clothing. Abr adras fabrics were used for men's chapan coats, kurtas, bedspreads, pillow covers, quilts, and upholstery for furniture.

The atlas weaving group includes fabrics made from pure silk, such as "four-ply" atlas, "eight-ply," and "twelve-ply" fabrics, also known as khon-atlas, as well as half-silk "yakroya." The more "plys" (tepklik) there are, the more luxurious the abr fabric becomes. According to the information from the weaver M. Mirzakirov from Margilan, khon-atlas was invented by the ruler of Kokand, Khudoyar Khan, in 1856, and that's why it is called khon-atlas. Initially, this precious fabric was reserved for the clothes of the Khan's family members. The homeland of khon-atlas is Margilan.

In Uzbek national artistic fabrics, color has played an important role. Each region of Uzbekistan is associated with traditional color schemes and combinations. According to the information from Margilan weaver M. Mirzakirov, the fabrics from Khujand featured red colors, Fergana used fewer reds but included saffron and yellow hues, and the fabrics from Kokand were dominated by blue and azure colors. Based on the density and color of the fabric, it was possible to determine where it was made. Additionally, each color was meant for a specific age group. Bukhara fabrics typically used dark red, yellow, and pink colors. Fergana fabrics featured a palette of seven colors: yellow, dark red, green, blue, pink, purple, and black. The blending of one color into another and the subtle impact of the background created a harmonious color effect. [7].

The color of the arqoq thread adds warmth to the entire color palette of the fabric, uniting different colors harmoniously. Arqoq thread typically came in three colors: dark red, yellow, and white. The dark red arqoq gave the fabric a muted pink tone, while the yellow arqoq added a silvery sheen, and the white arqoq conveyed a sense of calmness and stability.

Special finishing treatments have been an ancient practice in Central Asia. To give fabrics like atlas a shiny effect and create a moire effect on adras or beqasam fabrics, egg whites were used. The edge of the fabric would be dipped in egg whites, and the dry areas would be treated.

Then, the craftsman would use a wooden mallet, known as a "kudung," to press the fabric and ensure the moisture was evenly distributed throughout. Nowadays, this process is performed with finishing machines.

Abr fabrics feature a wide variety of patterns, which can be categorized into several groups: geometric, floral, zoomorphic, object-based, astral, and narrative[8]. Geometric patterns include circles, diamonds, squares, straight lines, and curved lines, among others. Floral motifs are relatively few but include designs such as "karam leaf," "nomoshom flower," "tree," "flower in a bowl," "almond," "pear," "branch," "pomegranate," and others. Object-based patterns are the most common and include depictions of items like "belt," "plank," "comb," "scythe," "bowl flower," "drum," "drum mask," "grain grinder," "sunshade," "sand container," "flag," "square," "chain," "moon axe," and more.

These patterns reflect the diversity and richness of Central Asian visual culture and the deep connection between daily life, nature, and art in the region.

Zoomorphic patterns in abr fabrics include representations of animals and their features, such as: "ram's horn," "tiger's tail," "camel's sock," "butterfly," "scorpion," "snake's trace," "hawk," "fairy rooster," "peacock," "crow," and others. These patterns are inspired by the natural world and reflect the cultural significance of these animals[9].

Another group of motifs includes complex representations where the meaning is derived from their names, often based on historical or legendary figures. Some examples include: "Oftobxon" and "Xosiyatxon" (named after famous craftsmen), "Domlajon" (named after the designer), "Farhod va Shirin," "Layli va Majnun," "Toxir va Zuxra," and others.[10] These motifs are rich with cultural references and stories.

In the 20th century, new patterns and colors were created to reflect contemporary themes, including: "Pobeda" (Victory), "O'zbekiston," "Kreml," "Sputnik," "Night Radiance," "Silk Road," "Indira," "Chess," "Samarkand Gate," "Ring Eye," "Gulnora," "Spinning Wheel," "Droplet," "Fergana Sunrise," "Navruz Butterfly," "International," and many more. These designs represent the evolution of Central Asian art, blending traditional techniques with modern influences.

The special type of abr-patterned fabric is known as duxobas or baxmal (or maxmal). This type of fabric features a fluffy base onto which the abr pattern is applied. In baxmal, the abr pattern is created in both length and width, with a shiny finish. The abr pattern is divided into three sections: a large central design with smaller patterns on the sides. In the 19th century, Bukhara artisans produced shoyi or nimshoyi fabrics (arqoq thread made from cotton, with a base made from tanda or arqoq cotton thread, and tuki made from shoyi). These duxobas were intricately woven with abr patterns that enhanced the visual appeal of the fabric.[11]

In the attire of the nobility, patterned silk fabrics such as baxmals, kimxobs, kundals, farangils, and atlas produced in France and Russia were commonly used. In addition to these, woolen fabrics (movut) were widely used for men's outer garments. These luxurious fabrics not only represented the status of their wearers but also reflected the influence of foreign trade and cultural exchange, especially in the Central Asian region.

In the 19th century, the main fabrics used for sewing traditional Uzbek clothing included cotton fabrics, silk, nimshoyi (a type of semi-silk fabric), and woolen fabrics. There were many types of cotton fabrics, with light brown and yellowish bo'z being the most common. These fabrics were widely used for making coats (chopon), as well as inner clothing and shawls for all ages. For women's headscarves, dakana (head coverings), and lacha (another type of headscarf), doka (a

type of cotton fabric) was commonly used. Men's shirts were typically made from coarse cotton fabric such as xomsurp and sidirg'a chit (a type of thin cloth), while more durable cotton fabrics were used for outerwear. The patterned cotton fabric called olachalar was more commonly used for making coats (chopon).

In the sewing of chopon (traditional outerwear), various fabrics were used, including bo'z (cotton), karbos, bosma, olacha, and yo'l-yo'l nimshoyi materials. In cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Kokand, Margilan, Namangan, and others, traditional Uzbek clothing made from silk fabrics (kanovuz, shoyi, xon-atlas), nimshoyi fabrics (beqasam, banoras, adras) were worn by wealthy individuals[12]

Methods

The dictionary provides descriptions of the following materials: Adras (a type of silk fabric), Abrband adras (silk fabric made using the abr technique), Atlas (a luxurious silk fabric), Banoras (another type of silk fabric), Baxmal (velvet or velvet-like fabric), Duxoba (a special type of patterned fabric), Yarimduxoba (a type of half-velvet fabric), Velvet and half velvet (smooth, soft fabrics), Beqasam (silk fabric), Bo'z qalami (a type of cotton fabric), Zarbof matolar (rich, decorative fabrics), Ip gazlama (cotton fabric), Janda-janda (another kind of fine fabric), Karbos (a type of fabric), Kimxob (a fabric used for making luxurious garments), Movut (woolen fabric), Mo'yna (fur or wool), Olacha (cotton fabric), Parpasha (a type of decorative cloth), Parcha (pieces of fabric), Podshoyi (a luxury fabric), Satin (smooth, glossy fabric), Surp oqlangan (polished or treated fabric), Shoyi (silk fabric), Nimshoyi (semi-silk fabric), Xon-atlas (special silk fabric from the Margilan region), Chit (cotton cloth), Qalami (a type of cloth) (see Table 1).

Climate is considered the most important natural factor that regulates almost all areas of human life and activity. When analyzing meteorological data, it is important to always keep in mind that they are relevant to a specifically selected location and are measured in a strict method.

The average multi-year maximum air temperature in Tashkent is +40.7°C, with the highest recorded temperature of 44.6°C in the summer of 1997. The average multi-year minimum air temperature is -15.5°C, and the lowest temperature ever recorded during the observation period was -29.5°C in the winter of 1930-1931. In summer, the weather in Tashkent is hot but stable, while in winter, it is highly variable. Uzbekistan's continental climate is influenced by its geographical location, solar radiation, and atmospheric circulation.

In the republic, the average temperature in July varies from 26°C in the north to 50°C in the south. In January, the average air temperature reaches -8°C in the north and 0°C in the south. The microclimate under clothing is measured in laboratories using standard tests on materials and clothing items.

Tashkent - Fergana fabrics

Tests using clothing allow for the evaluation of the user's subjective reaction to the garment. In practice, these experimental studies are conducted in specialized microclimate chambers. The design of the chamber enables the simulation and control of meteorological and specific environmental parameters, such as air movement, temperature, humidity, pressure variations, the presence of harmful substances, and others.

Currently, such chambers are widely used abroad, but they are not practically applied in our country. Creating such a chamber requires significant effort and costs. Therefore, a device has been developed to determine the parameters of the microclimate under clothing, and it was decided to use this device. This device allows for the complex measurement of temperature, humidity, and

steam gas concentration in the clothing space, with the ability to transmit data directly to the mobile application of the phone via Bluetooth.

To comprehensively measure the temperature, humidity, and steam gas concentration in the clothing space, a specific area was designated, and multi-layer suits were tested at temperatures ranging from a maximum of +30°C to a minimum of -10°C. Based on the static data of the climatic temperature in the designated areas, the seasonal maximum and minimum temperatures were calculated, and the average temperature was determined and checked.

Table 1. Classification of fabrics used in women's clothing in the Tashkent- Fergana region.

The software code for this device was developed using the "Arduino-1.8" program. The device consists of the following components: ESP-32 WiFi+Bluetooth: A modern microcontroller that allows the creation of remotely controlled Internet devices. CJMCU-811 CCS811: A digital gas sensor with low energy consumption, combined with a CCS801 sensor for detecting air quality, including carbon dioxide (CO₂) and a wide range of volatile organic compounds (VOCs). It also integrates an 8-bit MCU analog-to-digital converter (ADC) for precise measurement.

This is a low-energy consumption device used in battery-powered equipment, characterized by high sensitivity and rapid heating. The device is attached to the inner clothing for 64 minutes. Data on the microclimate parameters of temperature, humidity, and carbon dioxide under the clothing is transmitted to a mobile phone.

For multi-layered women's clothing, the microclimate parameters under the clothing at a temperature of +30°C were determined using the CJMCU-811 CCS811 device.

Diagram 1. Regional results of the air temperature under clothing. This diagram shows that in the Surkhandarya- Kashkadarya region, at a temperature of +30°C, the air temperature under clothing is 31.4°C, which is higher compared to other regions.

Diagram 2. Regional results of the air humidity under clothing. This diagram shows that in the Tashkent- Fergana region, at a temperature of +30 °C, the air humidity under clothing 30%,

which is higher compared to other regions.

Diagram 3. The result of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the air gap under clothing by regions. This diagram shows that in the Khorezm region, at a temperature of +30 oC , the CO₂ concentration in the air gap under clothing is 678 ppm, which is higher compared to other regions.

Results

Table 1. The result of clothing microclimate parametr indictors by regions at a temperature of +30 °C

№		The result of clothing microclimate parametr indictors by regions at a temperature of +30 °C				
		Tashkent-Fergana	Samakand-Bukhara	Surkhandarya-Kashkadarya	Khorezm	Karakalpak
1	Air temperature (T, °C),	29.6 °C	30.6 °C	31.4 °C	27.2 °C	29.5 °C
2	Air humidity (φ, %)	30%	26%	28%	24%	28%
3	Carbon monoxide	618 ppm	452 ppm	454 ppm	678 ppm	434 ppm

	(CO ₂ , ppm)				
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The clothing microclimate parametrs under multi –layered women’s clothing at - 10 °C were determined by the CJMCU-811 CCS811 device across different regions.

Diagram 4. The result of air temperature in the space under clothing by regions. This diagram shows that in the Samarkand-Bukhara region, at an outdoor temperature of -10 °C, the air temperature in the space under clothing is 32,8 °C , which is higher compared to other regions.

Diagram 5. The result of air humidity in the space under clothing by regions. This diagram shows that in the Karakalpak region, at an outdoor temperature of -10 °C , the air humidity in the space under clothing is 31%, which is higher compared to other regions.

Diagram 6. The result of carbon dioxide(CO₂) in the air gap under clothing by regions. This diagram shows that in the Samarkand-Bukhara region, at an outdoor temperature of -10 °C, the CO₂ concentration in the air gap under clothing is 2419 ppm, which is higher compared to

other regions.

Table 2. The results of clothing microclimate parametr indicators by regions at a temperature of -10°C

№		The results of clothing microclimate parametr indicators by regions at a temperature of -10°C				
		Tashkent-Fergana	Samarkand-Bukhara	Surkhandarya-Kashkadarya	Khorezm	Karakalpakstan
1	Air temperature (T, °C),	28,50 °C	32,80 °C	24,50 °C	24,40 °C	23,40 °C
2	Air humidity (φ, %)	22,00 %	30,00 %	22,00 %	24,00 %	31,00 %
3	Carbon dioxide CO ₂ (CO ₂ , ppm)	1212 ppm	2419 ppm	1846 ppm	1607 ppm	1134 ppm

a)

b)

Fig. 2. a) a device for determining clothing microclimate parameter; b) the schematic diagram of a device for determining clothing microclimate parameter indicators.

The summarized results of the experimental test are presented in the table

Table 3. The overall results of the experimental parameters of the air gap under clothing

Air temperature (T, °C), Air humidity (φ, %) Carbon dioxide (CO ₂ , ppm)	The results of clothing microclimate parameter indicators by regions at a temperature of +30 °C				
	Tashkent-Fergana	Samarkand-Bukhara	Surkhandarya-Kashkadarya	Khorezm	Karakalpakstan
T=+30 °C,	29.6 °C	30.6 °C	31.4 °C	27.2 °C	29.5 °C
	30,00%	26,00%	28,00%	24,00%	28,00%
	618 ppm	452 ppm	454 ppm	678 ppm	434 ppm
T=-10 °C,	28,50 °C	32,80 °C	24,50 °C	24,40 °C	23,40 °C
	22,00 %	30,00 %	22,00 %	24,00 %	31,00 %
	1212 ppm	2419 ppm	1846 ppm	1607 ppm	1134 ppm

Conclusion

The results of the experiment showed that at an average air temperature of +30°C and -10°C, the air exchange within the clothing cavity indicated that clothing in each region was suitable for both hot and cold air temperatures.

By determining the humidity inside the clothing, the psychological comfort level of the clothing can be evaluated. To maintain a comfortable microclimate, the humidity inside the clothing should not exceed 40%. The following equation was determined:

$$K_p = \phi/40$$

where:

is the relative coefficient of psychological comfort, is the humidity inside the clothing cavity, in %.

Table 4. Evaluating the psychological comfort level of clothing

Relative coefficient of psychological comfort, K_p	Clothing comfort level, ball
0,5-1,0	3
0,25-0,49; 1,01-1,25	2
0,25 lower; 1,25 higher	1

Thus, the values of – the relative coefficient of psychological comfort (shown in the table) – describe the following:

A value between (0.5–1.0) indicates a comfortable microclimate inside the clothing. A value between (0.25– 0.49; 1.01–1.25) indicates a subcomfort microclimate inside the clothing. Values below 0.25 and above 1.25 indicate an uncomfortable microclimate inside the clothing.

Table 5. Determining the relative coefficient of psychological comfort level by regions

№	Names of regions	T=+30 °C, Air humidity (ϕ , %)	K_p	T=-10 °C, Air humidity (ϕ , %)	K_p
1.	Tashkent-Fergana	30,00%	0,7	22,00 %	0,5
2.	Samarkand-Bukhara	26,00%	0,6	30,00 %	0,7
3.	Surkhandarya-Kashkadarya	28,00%	0,7	22,00 %	0,5
4.	Khorezm	24,00%	0,6	24,00 %	0,6
5.	Karakalpakstan	28,00%	0,7	31,00 %	0,9

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